

5G META

D.7.1

Dissemination & Communications Strategy

www.5gmeta-project.eu

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
DM	Dissemination Manager
DS	Deployment Site
EU	Europe/European
e.g.	Example
ICT	Information Communication Technology
ITS	Intelligent Transport System
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
No.	Number
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
ppt	PowerPoint
PR	Public Relations
R&D	Research & Development
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
TDM	Technical Dissemination Manager
TIER	Trust and Identity in Education and Research
V2X	Vehicle to everything
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The 5GMETA Dissemination and Communication Strategy includes the project's overall communication strategy as described in the Grant Agreement. It identifies the target audiences to be addressed during the project life-span and presents the dissemination and communication activities and channels that will be used throughout the project. This document also describes how the Dissemination and Communication will be managed, as well as the contribution expected from the partners in the consortium. This document includes a non-exhaustive list of graphic items associated with the project (the branding), and instructions on how to use them. This deliverable is a living document and will be updated following the periodic review. In its updates, a report on dissemination activities will be published including the list of activities the project consortium took part in and on the efficiency of the different communication channels.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project introduction

5GMETA is an H2020 project running from 1 September 2020 to 29 February 2024 with a 6-month extension and deployed by a consortium of 12 partners. 5GMETA open platform aims to leverage car-captured data to stimulate, facilitate, and feed with them innovative products and services. As a result, 5GMETA will empower the automotive ecosystem from industry players to new entrants, such as SMEs and high-tech start-ups, granting access to interoperable car-captured data according to data licenses. The access to data coming from relevant geographical regions will generate new opportunities and business models coming from valuable services, where data liability and billing will rely on an accountability dashboard of dataflow subscription and volume consumption.

5GMETA expands 5G network functions to enable data monetisation with a secure and private pipeline that manages data computing, dataflows according to service subscriptions and geographic queries. 5GMETA will realise demonstrators in terms of data heterogeneity, value creation, and business models to ensure that the interests and requirements of third parties and new players are considered beyond traditional automotive industries. 5GMETA will focus on technology transfer activities to incubators and clusters, performing different dissemination, tutorials, and hackathons to capture the attention of SMEs and high-tech start-ups with a platform leading to new opportunities in an incoming profitable market.

1.2 Purpose of the deliverable

The present deliverable, D7.1 clearly identifies the overall dissemination and communication strategy to be followed throughout the project duration, to achieve maximum impact among the different stakeholders, not least among the general public. This report will be followed by a first report on dissemination activities in M22 and a final report on dissemination activities in M42. The purpose of the document is to define target users and other stakeholder clusters, and the key messages and material to be used. It will also define the types and mix of communication media to be used per target group and a timeline for different activities including events. Finally, key performance indicators will be defined to provide measurable targets and outcomes of the 5GMETA dissemination and communication strategy.

This document also aims to map all communication activities for 5GMETA and describes how different set of communication tools and techniques will be used to reach specific target audiences. It will serve as the comprehensive and central listing for all communication activities and events over the course of the project.

1.3 Intended audience

This is a public document, and can be consulted by the European Commission, 5GMETA's consortium partners as well as external stakeholders.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables

This deliverable addresses the 5GMETA project communication strategy in Section 2 including the target groups, key messages to be shared with the said groups, communication channels, and collaborative communication approach. In Section 3, communication means including the visual identity of the project, online presence strategy except for the website, which is thoroughly described in D7.2, media articles for the website and external channels, images and photographs are described. Furthermore, Section 4 describes communication activities including the hackathons, events and

conferences, peer-reviewed publications, white papers, and liaison activities. Section 5 defines the roles and responsibilities for dissemination activities, including the dissemination manager and technical dissemination manager, communication management group and partners' responsibilities as well as the dissemination and communication reporting. Section 6 is devoted to KPI targets while Section 7 addresses the timing of the communication activities.

This deliverable defines the main communication strategy for the project and has tight connections with WP6 in terms of activities such as hackathons engaging new actors in the industry. It is also closely related to exploitation strategy, which is to be addressed in the deliverables D7.4 and D7.5. This deliverable does not address the ethics requirements, which are defined in WP8 deliverables.

1.5 Main changes from the previous version

The main changes in this version of the deliverable compared to the previous version are as follows:

- Document has been proofread and refined.
- The project timeline in Section 1.2 has been updated in the light of the 6-month extension.
- Added the Section 1.4 on Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables
- Target groups in Section 2.1 have been adapted to be more project-specific.
- Added the Section 2.3 Collaborative Communication Approach to include plans to collaborate with other similar projects.
- Added Section 4.1 about hackathons.
- The events and conference targets in Section 4.2 have been updated to be more project-specific and based on input from the consortium partners.
- The publication targets in Section 4.3 have been updated to be more project-specific and based on the consortium partners' planning to publish technical and/or scientific papers.
- Added Section 4.4 about White Papers as dissemination targets.
- KPI targets in Section 6 have been updated according to the feedback received from all partners and their individual dissemination goals which have also been implemented into the deliverable as a separate table (cf. Table 8).
- Project timeline in Section 7.1 Official deliverables has been updated in the light of 6-month extension.

2 COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

The principal objectives of the 5GMETA communication strategy are to:

- Disseminate the project's results to the widest audience possible, engage scientific, technical, business, institutional, and governmental audiences (EU-wide and globally) and encourage feedback.
- Build relationships, through networking with existing related projects, initiatives, and services, to share knowledge and spread good practice through coordination/clustering activities. In particular, this will include liaison with entities (projects, platforms, organisations) linked to 5GMETA partners. This will include identifying influential industry, governance, policy and technology experts, and potential customers, based on partners' involvement in other initiatives and associations.
- Create interesting information that can be disseminated through social media networks and that will result in positive media coverage for the project at national and European level.
- Communicate and raise awareness about the project's objectives, which are:
 - **To create a platform to ingest and deliver car data:** 5GMETA will develop and integrate a set of 5G network functions by applying service slicing for data delivery based on IoT architectures and technologies. This will capture, process, and deliver in a distributed and configurable manner the data coming from vehicles that are publishing driving dynamics and position, road environment, driver behaviour, and passenger services activity collected from sensors and devices.
 - **To generate innovative CAM services and applications:** 5GMETA will develop, integrate, train, and test a set of exploitable demonstrators implementing innovative CAM use cases and covering heterogeneous datasets, business models, and industry segments to widely represent the expected features, APIs, and pricing which would fit into new applications or players beyond 5GMETA consortium.
 - **To generate business opportunities:** 5GMETA will capture all the service developer's needs to define a methodology, tutorials, integration and operation samples and guides to allow fast prototyping and exploitation of new business opportunities.
 - **To define new business models:** 5GMETA will declare new perspectives to support traditional and new players of the wider automotive industry ecosystem to cooperate to monetise car data exploited on innovative CAM services and applications. 5GMETA will catalyse databased applications for OEM/TIER1 providing a common bus to accelerate their R&D optimisation processes while granting to SMEs and high-tech start-ups the access to car data, which could feed their innovative services and ideas and generate revenues.
 - **To define 5G edge infrastructure life cycle:** 5GMETA will produce recommendations to drive effective implementation of 5G infrastructures adopting CAM business and policy perspectives. 5GMETA will define the foundations for the MEC architectures to serve as cloudlets for data-centric CAM services and applications enabling new business opportunities to MNOs and third parties in a cost-effective manner.

2.1 Target groups

The target audiences have been identified and agreed with the consortium and include the main types of interlocutors to whom the project will be distributing news and communicating the project services and benefits. The consortium will seek to engage with these stakeholders at different levels with different channels. This is a non-exhaustive list, which will be updated and monitored to make sure that all relevant stakeholders are addressed for the results exploitation.

The main target audiences include:

- **Industries, SMEs, and startups** (for business exploitation): Including but not limited to Tier 1 suppliers such as vehicle manufacturers and automotive suppliers; ICT & software suppliers; infrastructure suppliers; insurance companies; cloud providers and telecoms; smart sensor providers.
- **Institutions** (for implementation and follow-up/take-up aspects): Including but not limited to policy and decision makers at European, national, or regional level; local, regional or national public authorities; standardisation bodies; national authorities for privacy; national or regional funding bodies; road operators and traffic management centres, public authorities, cities; public transport operators and mobility and transport related public bodies; coordinated emergency response control centres; private and public organisations in Europe who constitute the route-to-market for the implementation aspects of 5GMETA's work
- **Scientific and research community** (for cross-fertilisation and transfer of results to follow-up initiatives): Including but not limited to academic and research institutions; operators of test sites and living labs to integrate piloted V2X technologies for future applications; other research initiatives covering synergistic subject matters.
- **Users and general public** (for acceptance, usability, and impact assessment as well as take-up aspects): Including but not limited to sector or geographical organisations of industrial end users e.g., clusters or user associations; user groups impacted by 5G technologies e.g., public transport operators, mobile operators; end-user associations e.g., citizen associations interested in security/privacy issues; end-user communities who can work with early end-users on training and organisational development.

2.2 Key messages

To effectively promote 5GMETA, a set of messages have been defined and tailored for each of the targeted audience groups:

Table 1: 5GMETA general messages

Target	Key message
Industries, SMEs and startups	5GMETA will stimulate, facilitate, and feed innovative products and services and generate business opportunities, especially for SMEs and startups. Also, 5GMETA will generate business opportunities by capturing all the service developer's needs to define a methodology, tutorials, integration and operation samples and guides to allow fast prototyping and exploitation of new business opportunities.
Institutions	5GMETA will produce recommendations to drive effective implementation of 5G infrastructures, adopting CAM business and policy perspectives.
Scientific and research community	5GMETA will develop, integrate, train and test a set of exploitable demonstrators implementing innovative CCAM use cases and covering heterogeneous datasets, business models and industry segments to widely represent the expected features, APIs and pricing which would fit into new applications or players beyond 5GMETA consortium.

Users and general public	5GMETA will increase safety and security of data, ensuring data privacy and providing new services concerning transport safety and mobility services (e.g., parking) in urban areas.
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2.3 Collaborative Communication Approach

Apart from the set-in-place communication strategy to disseminate the 5GMETA project objectives, achievements, events, and activities, joint activities (e.g. workshops, webinars, sessions in conferences) will be organised with similar data-driven projects.

Currently, there is a collaboration agreement with 5G-LOGINNOV, which is a project that received funding under the same call as 5GMETA and is coordinated by ERTICO.

2.4 Communication Channels

The communication channels identified in this deliverable have as main objective to implement the dissemination and communication strategy, to ensure widespread dissemination of project information, to engage with relevant stakeholders and to create understanding of the project results so as to facilitate their exploitation. The following activities will be carried out as part of the task:

- Design and publish a public project website to be used as the main information platform.
- Publish periodic news reporting on the project activities, outcomes, and events.
- Establish a social media presence on existing channels.
- Design and produce, as necessary, project leaflets and other marketing materials such as posters/banners, videos, etc.

Table 2 below identifies communication channels and tools relevant to the different target groups. These channels and tools will help convey the general and technical messages developed during the project.

Table 2: Target groups and communication tools/channels

Target Groups	Project website	Social media	Video clips/ project video	Non scientific articles	Printed material	Newsletters (ERTICO/ project partners)	PowerPoint presentations	Events	B2B meetings	Conf. calls
General public	X	X	X	X		X	X		X	
Industries	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Institutions	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Scientific and research community	X		X		X	X	X	X	X	X
Users	X	X	X	X		X	X		X	

3 COMMUNICATION MEANS

The communication plan will develop material to effectively ensure 5GMETA information flow, create awareness and reach out to target audiences. The following indicative list of proposed communication materials shows the tools already selected to communicate and disseminate about the project:

- Visual identity: Project logo and branding guidelines, project templates for Word and PowerPoint.
- Printed material: Factsheet, brochure, technical leaflets, roll-up posters.
- Online presence: Website, social media.
- Featured articles: Online newsletters, press and other articles.
- Infographics and other media materials: e.g. photographs, video(s).

The following approach should be adopted for the selected promotional material and campaigns:

- **Promotional material:** Promotion materials for the project, including articles and press releases, should be translated, when possible, into the languages of the project partners when relevant. Partners will be responsible for the in-house translation of press releases, leaflets, or other short news articles for the website.
- **Communication campaigns:** In general, ERTICO will initiate communication campaigns and will then send requests to partners, in order to contribute to the deliverables. ERTICO will also draft a work plan for all the activities related to WP7 and distribute resources amongst the partners. Some typical communication campaigns and activities include the organisation of events; representation of the project in European and international events; media campaigns and conferences when relevant; regular updates of the website and liaison with the media.

3.1 Visual identity, project logo and other promotional material

The 5GMETA logo must appear on every project related item (documents, banners, videos, giveaways, etc.). The possible uses of the logo, the pantone, font, and related guidelines are illustrated in Annex 2: 5GMETA Logo and Uses.

5GMETA templates for MS Word documents (deliverable reports, meeting minutes, and agenda) and Power Point presentations have been developed based on the project visual identity in Month 2.

More information about printed and online materials can be found in D7.2 report and other communication materials.

3.2 Online presence: website and social media

The website is thoroughly described in D7.2 5GMETA Website and other communication materials.

Social media will be used to raise the visibility of 5GMETA's project news and events and engage with a wider audience in a two-way conversation, to encourage the exchange of opinions and ideas. Consortium partners will employ their organisations' and personal Twitter and LinkedIn accounts to inform the audience about 5GMETA's results, successes, events, webinars, workshops, etc.

The project will not create its own Twitter and LinkedIn accounts, which would require establishing a base of subscribers from scratch but will rather use the well-established accounts of the project partners. A list of identified partners' Twitter and LinkedIn accounts has been initiated and will be updated throughout the project's lifespan.

Table 3: 5GMETA partners' social media channels

Project partner	LinkedIn company page	Twitter account
ERTICO	Yes	@ERTICO
DEKRA	Yes	@dekradigital
Intempora	Yes	@INTEMPORA
AKKA	Yes	@AKKA_Tech
NeoGLS	Yes	@NeoGLS
UNIMORE	Yes	@UNIMORE_univ
LINKS	Yes	@LinksFoundation
VEDECOM	Yes	@vedecom
ICOOR	Yes	@ICOOR1
Vicomtech	Yes	@Vicomtech
WINDTRE	Yes	@WindTreOfficial
LIFTT	Yes	No

In addition, the Dissemination Manager may require WP7 members to contribute to the identification of LinkedIn groups in which 5GMETA content can be promoted. This strategy will allow the project to reach a wider audience and engage in online discussions. An initial table is contained in D7.2.

Tweets and LinkedIn posts can be either initiated by all project partners or follow an input coming from the project's website, hence, an article, content or event. For both LinkedIn and Twitter, project partners must use the project hashtag #5GMETA, as this will not only allow an optimal promotion of the project, but also the monitoring of the social media posts and outreach.

In addition to partners' own initiatives, the Dissemination Manager may share with the partners involved in WP7 and/or the whole consortium a list of Tweets and/or LinkedIn posts to be published on partners' channels to boost the online presence of the project.

Such actions aim at fulfilling the KPIs set in the project proposal. For this purpose, the social media performance of 5MGETA will be regularly monitored and discussed during the periodic WP7 calls.

Further information regarding 5GMETA's social media channels can be found in D7.2 5GMETA Website and other communication materials.

3.3 Web and external media articles

5GMETA partners, coordinated by the Dissemination Manager (DM), will write articles and interviews for inclusion on the website. Some longer features will be prepared for possible inclusion in external media (such as Intelligent Transport, ITS International, etc) and magazines. ERTICO will also target individual/freelance journalists thanks to the PR platform they manage (Meltwater). Articles and editorials published will cover the project objectives and results presentation as well as more specific issues (e.g. standards).

Press releases will be published by the consortium at key milestones during the lifetime of the project. ERTICO will prepare the press releases in English and present them, before publication, to the partners directly involved, for comments and input (e.g. quotes).

The final press releases shall be circulated to the whole consortium for relaying through their corporate channels, after translation and adaptation for local audiences, as well as distribution to the national media contacts. The press release will be distributed through Meltwater, a tool used by ERTICO, as well as to all other international media in partners' own press list.

During the project, the Consortium will produce and publish articles in English or other languages to get media interest and encourage magazines to publish articles on the project services and benefits.

Each partner who writes an article, especially if planned for an external media, will inform the DM about articles that are to be published in their national media before publication, in order to inform other project partners so that they can object to the inclusion of any sensitive/ confidential/ proprietary information.

3.4 Infographics and other media materials

Some professional photographs might be purchased¹, and graphics developed, for the promotion of the project in dissemination and communication materials and channels (e.g. presentations, brochures, articles, website, etc.), on a per need basis. At important events and milestones, a professional photographer/ camera operator could be hired to take pictures/ videos at events and demonstrations.

¹ If the images are copyrighted, the source must be mentioned.

4 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

The following set of activities will enable a strong proactive and reactive communications effort. These actions will follow a clear strategy and action plan with three different phases:

- **Awareness building phase** (making the project known): to raise awareness on 5GMETA's motivation and reasoning behind the project.
- **Participation phase** (targeting defined user groups): to let identified target groups understand the concepts of 5GMETA and the achieved results. In this phase, presentations and examples will be disseminated through the web portal and selected events.
- **Action** (influencing practices, products and standards): to receive feedback in the form of demonstration of the results, alternative approaches or new reference implementations. This phase will include events with project results users, gathering new requirements for 5GMETA, etc.

4.1 Hackathons

The 5GMETA project has been conceived since its inception to have an impact in terms of creating high-tech start-ups or new business opportunities for SMEs, and to achieve a relevant involvement of SMEs. Coherently with such a strategic vision of the project, two hackathons will be organized to capture SMEs and high-tech start-ups interest towards 5GMETA platform for car-database services. To pursue such objective, the two hackathons are planned with two distinct focuses: the first one will be business-oriented, while the second will be technology-oriented.

Deliverable D6.3 *Strategy for engaging new actors* describes in details the rationale behind the two events and outlines the plan of actions to be followed by the 5GMETA consortium for their organization.

In particular, the communication activities to be carried out before the events have a crucial importance in ensuring the success of the hackathons. It is fundamental to raise awareness about the events starting well in advance and putting in place the proper communication actions to reach the target audience. The goal is to involve around 70 participants for each hackathon (medium-sized event). On one side, this is a good number to achieve proper cross-fertilisation and interaction between participants that are fundamental aspects to produce valuable outcomes for the project.

5GMETA consortium partners will take several steps to ensure the engagement of the hackathon participants is kept alive after the event, i.e. the participants will be invited to provide regular updates about the 5GMETA platform.

4.2 Events and conferences

The project will be presented at different levels (direct participation, stand, promotional materials, sessions, papers, online events, etc.) at events and conferences. The Consortium has identified a preliminary list of events where the project can be showcased, and will continue identifying other European and international events and appointments that could be relevant for the presentation and promotion of 5GMETA.

Table 4. List of target events & conferences

Project partner	Target events and / or conferences
AKKA	ITS World Congress
	EUCNC
	EU Data Viz

	International Conference on Open Source Systems and Technologies (ICOSST)
	IEEE International Conference on Data and Software Engineering (ICoDSE)
	Next Transport Research Arena (TRA) Conferences
	IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy 2022
DEKRA	ITS World Congress
ERTICO	ITS World Congress
	ITS European Congress
ICOOR	ITS European Congress
	Modena Motor Valley Festival 2022
	Modena Smart Life
	Next Transport Research Arena (TRA) Conferences
INTEMPORA	ITS World Congress
LIFTT	VTM 2022
	ITS European Congress
LINKS	ITS European Congress
	VTM
NeoGLS	ITS World Congress
	ITS European Congress
	IEEE ITSC
VEDECOM	ITS World Congress
	EuCNC
	IEEE VTC
VICOMTECH	ITS World Congress
	ITS European Congress
	EuCNC
	IEEE 5G World Forum
WINDTRE	Modena Motor Valley Festival
	Modena Smart Life

Target events, conferences, sessions, presentations, and thematic workshops will be organised during these events to present the project activities and results to expert, technical and scientific communities.

Each partner is required to share information about relevant events for the project or targeted events where the project is presented.

A reporting form (see Annex 1) will be made available to all partners to facilitate the collection of such information.

A list of events is presented in Table 4 and will be updated every year.

4.3 Peer-reviewed publications

As 5GMETA is an Innovation Action (IA) and not a Research and Innovation Action (RIA), most of the technical dissemination will be targeted to industrial or technical conferences with large attendance (e.g. ITS World Congress or EuCNC). However, the project will also look into publishing peer-reviewed articles in scientific and technical magazines and journals. In the following table, the identified target journals and magazines are listed. The publications, when restrictions do not apply, will be made publicly available on the project website.

Table 5: Target peer-reviewed journals and magazines

Target peer-reviewed journals and magazines	Motivation
IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine	Innovative 5GMETA use cases and business models enabled by 5G CAM and exploitable by new business actors.
IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine	5GMETA car data pipelining and monetization models for SLAs and licensing terms for platform and innovative data-based CAM services.
IEEE Network	5G MEC network functions for data processing and pipelining. Discussion of security and trust issues in IoT/edge/cloud network.
IEEE Consumer Electronics Magazine	Focused on the innovation aspects of the 5GMETA services for consumers.
IEEE Internet of Things Magazine	The generation, pipelining, representation, organization, storage, retrieval, and use of information in 5GMETA

4.4 White papers

5G-PPP white papers contain informed discussion of the 5G challenges as perceived by the members of the community. 5GMETA is aware of the contractual commitment to 5G-PPP and is committed to contributing to and on occasion, editing white papers related to the main topics of the project. Due to the nature of the project, which not only targets innovation on technical aspects but also on business models, White Papers are considered by 5GMETA as a significant dissemination mean for publishing non-scientific content.

In particular, the 5G Automotive Working Group has been identified as an interesting forum to share ideas and lessons learnt, and to potentially publish a position paper about data monetization in intelligent transportation systems. Two project partners, ERTICO and VICOM, had actively contributed to 5G-PPP white papers in previous projects and are members of the 5G Automotive Working Group.

4.5 Liaison activities

This section refers to liaison activities with the scope of engaging key external stakeholders (standardisation bodies, industry, public authorities) outside the consortium at both national and international level. The project partners will also identify key ongoing and future public and private initiatives and projects and serve as main contact point in creating a liaison with them. These activities, and how they will be carried out, will variate according to the nature, scope and objectives; from simple exchange information to mutual involvement in project activities, from mutual promotion to more structured and internal cooperation on findings and results.

5 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

ERTICO will be responsible for the overall coordination of communication and dissemination activities, including production of printed materials, maintenance of the website, drafting of articles and press releases etc. However, consortium members have budget allocated (person-months and other direct costs) for dissemination and are therefore required to contribute with inputs to news on the website, co-organisation of workshops and press events, presentations in conferences and third-party events, scientific publications (technical papers in conferences or scientific papers for peer-reviewed publications), translations, media contact, and monitoring in their countries.

ERTICO will monitor regularly the website and every 6 months will present an overview of the related statistics. In relation to the periodic review and internal project reporting, updates of the deliverable D7.1 will be provided either as internal reporting or through D7.3 and D7.6, including statistics of YouTube, Mail Chimp (mass-mailing campaigns), number of articles published, and participants in the project-organised events.

5.1 Dissemination Manager and Technical Dissemination Manager

The 5GMETA Dissemination Manager and Technical Dissemination Manager are respectively ERTICO and Vicomtech.

The Dissemination Manager at ERTICO will act, together with the Coordinator, as the spokesperson of the project. He/she will be the main contact point for the media and external stakeholders; responsible for communicating at European level and will work closely with the site leaders and other relevant members of the consortium in organising events, coordinating articles and translations.

The Dissemination Manager will report at least twice a year the achievements and communication strategy to the consortium (including website statistics, events, printed materials etc.). He/she will also define and monitor the consortium members' work plan for communication and dissemination.

The Technical Dissemination Manager (TDM) is in charge of the scientific and technical dissemination, and will coordinate activities such as papers and articles submissions to events and journals, demonstrations and project workshops programmes.

5.2 Communication management group

At the beginning of the project, each consortium member will be asked to provide contact details of the person responsible for communication and promotion of the project within the organisation. This contact should not necessarily be the official project contact, but rather a professional in communication, marketing and PR or, where this is not possible, with experience in communication and dissemination activities of European projects. These contacts will be included in the communication group which will discuss, in form of conference calls, specific issues such as organisation of large events, creation of promotional materials, production of a video etc.

The members of the consortium will have regular calls/meetings throughout the duration of the project. The consortium will meet at least once a year to discuss the progress of the project, which will allow them to also assess the effectiveness of the communication strategy.

5.3 Consortium partners

Consortium partners will contribute with inputs to news articles for the website, the events calendar and printed materials, as relevant and when required. They will report their project-related communication activities to ERTICO by including information related to the events they attended or which they are planning to attend, via the reporting form. They will also forward project related press clippings and web or video material that are published in their countries/companies. Furthermore, partners are encouraged to promote the project to their peers such as neighbouring city authorities, users and logistics providers or 5G and ITS related companies.

Partners are required to disseminate and publicise the project through their own channels (such as newsletters, websites, printed materials, etc.). Partners are also required to contact local media and other interest groups to raise the awareness of the project. In addition, ERTICO will be used as the information channel for reaching an ITS specialist audience working on development and deployment of ITS systems and services across Europe.

5.4 Dissemination and communication reporting

The participation of consortium partners in any event with an opportunity for dissemination and promotion of 5GMETA (conferences, workshops, etc.), as well as the performance of every dissemination activity related to 5GMETA (presentations, paper submissions, material distribution etc.), has to be communicated beforehand to the DM. Prior communication will ensure the optimal promotion of the content and the:

- Production of high-quality 5GMETA publications, presentations and other communication materials;
- Avoidance of overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- Monitoring and recording of project communication and dissemination activities in an effective and efficient way and their impact.

A reporting template has been created on Microsoft Teams for partners to fill in and update. This template is included in Annex 1. This will allow everyone to provide inputs as well as to be informed on dissemination activities in which other partners are involved.

5.4.1 Dissemination activities report

The partner who is involved in a dissemination activity should fill in the Dissemination and communication Excel file and store the dissemination material (final paper, presentation, poster etc.) in the dedicated folder set up in the project collaboration tool (Microsoft Teams). This does not limit to events but covers also articles, newsletter, internal meetings, technical presentations and sessions, scientific publications and papers. If possible, the partner should provide the DM with a couple of photos of their participation to an event / conference / workshop to feed the 5GMETA website and so as to collect relevant material to be used throughout the project implementation.

GDPR: If the material contains a reference to other partners or the name or photo of an individual, publishing this content should be agreed with the person/partner in question before the dissemination request is made.

Language: If the material is in a national language other than English, the procedure should still be followed. A brief description in English should be added (not a complete translation).

5.5 Acknowledgments

There are three types of acknowledgments that have to be added depending on the type of materials produced:

1. The following acknowledgement text should be included in **all publications related to the 5GMETA work**:

“This work is a part of the 5META project. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957360. This content reflects only the authors’ view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information this publication contains.”

2. For **other communication activities**, the EC emblem (flag)² should be added with the following sentence:

“This work is a part of the 5GMETA project. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957360.”

3. For **infrastructure, equipment and major results**, the EC emblem (flag) should be added with the following sentence:

“This [infrastructure] [equipment] [insert type of result] is part of the 5GMETA project. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957360.” Disclaimer

All deliverables will include a disclaimer:

The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The above referenced consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind including without limitation direct, special, indirect, or consequential damages that may result from the use of these materials subject to any liability which is mandatory due to applicable law. © 2020 by 5GMETA Consortium.

² Available at https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

6 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

Communication and dissemination activities must have the right impact on target stakeholders and advance the goals of the project. To make sure that the communication and dissemination strategy is implemented in an effective manner throughout the life of the project, there must be a good monitoring and evaluating mechanism in place. Although the true impact of the project's communication activities may be broader, quantitative indicators present some measurable values to help evaluate the degree to which the targets of the communication plan are met. 5GMETA has defined a set of KPIs and indicated a target value for each communication tool, channel, and activity. The KPIs will be regularly monitored and corrective actions will be taken as needed. Table 6 below describes the planned 5GMETA communication activities to be performed in the different project phases and KPIs expected from each of them.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, some disruptions might have happened, making it difficult to meet certain KPIs set in the project proposal, especially when it comes to certain types of events (workshops, demonstrations, etc.). Events greatly benefit website visits, the number of news produced in-house and from external media, as well as social media and the production of papers and scientific publications, which most of the time are presented at physical events. Another negative impact could also concern the number of people attending conferences and trade shows. Should these become on-line events, the presence of 1000/10.000 participants described in the project proposal may not be achievable. Should the pandemic negatively affect 5GMETA's KPIs, these shall be adjusted to the situation.

Table 6: KPI

Key performance indicator	Target value		
	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Website: Unique visitors per month	≥100	≥150	≥200
Session duration	≥2 min	≥2 min	≥2 min
Twitter: #5GMETA hashtag tweets and retweets	≥40	≥60	≥70
In-house videos: Number produced	≥1	≥2	≥3
Press releases / Articles per year	≥12	≥12	≥16
Project brochure: Number produced	1	Update	Update
Number of scientific and technical publications.	≥3 paper	≥8 papers	≥11 papers
Presentations at events and conferences and trade shows	≥5	≥16	≥17

Key performance indicator	Target value		
Total number of participants in 5GMETA webinars (in case no physical events can resume due to COVID)	≥30	≥40	≥50
No of stakeholders attending 5GMETA events (hackathons & final event)	n/a	≥45	≥70
No of hackathons with incubators	0	1	1

Table 7: Partner contribution to Publication and Event related KPIs

Partners	Scientific/Technical Publications			Presentations at events, conferences, and trade shows		
	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
AKKA	2	3	3	2	3	3
DEKRA	0	1	1	0	1	1
ERTICO	0	0	0	0	0	0
ICOOR	0	2	2	0	2	2
Intempora	0	0	0	0	0	1
LIFTT	0	0	0	0	1	1
LINKS	0	0	0	0	2	2
NeoGLS	0	0	0	0	2	2
VEDECOM	0	1	2	1	1	2
Vicomtech	1	1	3	2	2	3
WINDTRE	0	0	0	0	2	0
TOTAL	3	8	11	5	16	17

7 TIMING OF COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

7.1 Official deliverables

No particular disruption is foreseen for the submission of the deliverables listed below; however, D7.3 might have been impacted by COVID-19, should it continue to spread before M18. Should the participation to events be reduced and should there be no possible alternative concerning the organisation of webinars, the reporting on dissemination activities might be negatively affected and/ or delayed by one or two months.

Table 8: Official deliverables

Number	Title	Official delivery date
D7.1	Dissemination & communication strategy	Month 3
D7.2	5GMETA Website and other communication materials	Month 3
D7.3	First report on dissemination activities	Month 18
D7.4	5GMETA platform Commercialisation strategy	Month 18
D7.5	Report on the implementation of the 5GMETA platform Commercialisation strategy	Month 42
D7.6	Final report on dissemination activities	Month 42
D7.7	Recommendations to Authorities and Standardisation bodies	Month 42

7.2 Proposed timeline of activities

Considering the above-proposed activities, below is a preliminary timeline of activities:

Figure 1: Proposed dissemination timeline

Although dissemination activities (project workshops, events and conferences, scientific and technical publications, liaison activities) should be carried out during the entire lifespan of the project, some

actions might be more relevant than others depending on the development phase of 5GMETA. For instance, year 1 (2020 – 2021) will mostly focus on the awareness phase, however not excluding the participation in events and conferences and the action phase, should some results be already available.

In the same way, year 2 (2021 – 2022) should mostly focus on the participation phase, as the project should be mature enough to share preliminary results in congresses and via papers and publications. Moreover, year 3 (2022 – 2023) should mostly focus on the action phase, hence, influencing practices, products and standards and receiving feedback in the form of demonstration of the results.

Two key milestones that will require the involvement of the majority of the identified dissemination activities will be the two hackathons.

8 CONCLUSION

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy has identified and described the target groups for dissemination and communication activities and highlighted how and through which dissemination channels they will be reached. It described the main dissemination tools, which will be particularly important for outreach activities. This strategy has also identified key initiatives and EU funded projects with which to establish strategic alliances and collaboration mechanisms.

ANNEX 1: REPORTING TEMPLATE

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
	Name of dissemination activity	Type of dissemination	Start date	End date	Internal/External	Lead Partner	Other Partners/Organisations	City and Country	Link
1									
2	Smart mobility, WindTre in campo con il pr	General media	21/10/2020	21/10/2020	External	WINDTRE		Italy	htt
3	5GMETA kicks off, intent on revolutionising	General media	22/09/2020	22/09/2020	External	ERTICO		Belgium	
4	ERTICO announces the 5GMETA Project to	General media	3/8/2020	3/8/2020	External	ERTICO		Belgium	
5	ERTICO ANNOUNCES THE 5GMETA AND 5G	Newsletter/website	3/8/2020	3/8/2020	Internal	ERTICO		Belgium	htt
6	NEW 5G PROJECT INTENDS TO REVOLUTIC	Newsletter/website	22/9/2020	22/9/2020	Internal	ERTICO		Belgium	htt
7	Lancement du projet 5GMETA – Une révoli	General media	24/09/2020	24/09/2020	External	AKKA	Auto Innovations	NA	htt
8	AKKA: PARTICIPATION AU PROJET 5GMETA	General media	24/09/2020	24/09/2020	External	AKKA	Easy bourse	NA	htt
9	AKKA TECHNOLOGIES : PARTICIPATION AU	General media	24/09/2020	24/09/2020	External	AKKA	BFM bourse	NA	htt
10	Akka : participation au projet 5GMETA	General media	24/09/2020	24/09/2020	External	AKKA	Zone bourse	NA	htt
11	Akka : participation au projet 5GMETA	General media	24/09/2020	24/09/2020	External	AKKA	Boursama	NA	htt
12	Akka Technologies : lancement du projet 5	General media	23/9/2020	23/9/2020	External	AKKA	Orange	NA	htt
13	EU reveals final 5G funding under Horizon	General media	22/6/2020	22/6/2020	External	NA	Enterprise IoT insights	NA	htt
14	EU Boosts Investment In 5G Hardware Inn	General media	19/6/2020	19/6/2020	External	NA	Alert IFY	NA	htt
15									
16									
17									
18									

Figure 2: Reporting template

ANNEX 2: 5GMETA LOGO, FONT AND THEIR USES

It is important that the project has a distinct identity and branding that can be clearly recognised as 5GMETA. This is why a set of graphics, including fonts, colours and guidelines (use of the logo) have been developed.

The graphics can be used freely by all consortium members, however, all external bodies, except for the European Commission, must ask for permission before using them.

The name of the project is 5GMETA. The logo is meant to appear on every project related item (documents, banners, videos, giveaways, etc.). Below all the possible uses of the logo, the pantone and font, and guidelines on how to use them are illustrated.

ERTICO has created a bold, versatile logo for 5GMETA. 5GMETA's logo has two key elements: the symbol and the letters. The symbol is composed of two images: a steering wheel and the Wi-Fi symbol. The steering wheel represents the automotive industry, while the Wi-Fi symbol is a direct link to connectivity and 5G. Both elements combined fully represent the concept behind 5GMETA. The shape is dynamic, and the colour range is exciting and energetic.

The colours for the project are aquamarine and ERTICO's 'Connected & Automated driving' focus colour. These two colours perfectly fade into each other and provide many design possibilities for the production of branding material.

Figure 3: 5GMETA master logo

The logo has several options (positive and negative included) for different uses, as outlined in these guidelines, for different reproduction purposes (presentations, brochures, roll-ups, website, etc.).

The master logo should always appear intact. The text should never be amended or removed. Each element and its position in relation to each other have been carefully designed and must never be stretched, altered or distorted. Master logos for all applications are available for use in the Microsoft Teams collaborative platform or by contacting ERTICO's communications department. Always follow these guidelines to ensure a consistent use. Colour is a powerful means of identification. Consistent use of 5GMETA's logo colours will help build visibility and recognition for the project and will distinguish it from other competitors.

The colour logo is made of a range of colours: users should always try to use the full colour logo on a white background.

Figure 4: 5GMETA 100% black logo

Figure 5: 5GMETA reversed logo

In situations where the logo must be reproduced in black and white, the one-colour logo should be used. In situations where the logo must appear on a dark coloured background, then the one-colour reversed logo should be used.

Regarding the colour, 5GMETA uses a limited palette to build a strong recognition of the project.

Core colours: Strong colours are used within the master logo. They can be used carefully as highlight or background colours in documents also.

Secondary colours: Any secondary colours should be chosen to neutrally compliment the core colours and should be used sensitively with these colours. Always ensure that white, and 5GMETA core colours are more dominant.

	Focus: Connected & Automated driving	Secondary colour
PANTONE 2226	PANTONE Violet C	PANTONE 2129 C
C = 60 M = 0 Y = 23 K = 0	C = 94 M = 0 Y = 100 K = 0	C = 0 M = 69 Y = 35 K = 0
R = 87 G = 197 B = 203	R = 65 G = 0 B = 153	R = 110 G = 137 B = 197
#57c5cb	#451683	#6e89c5

Figure 6: 5GMETA core and secondary colours

Incorrect use of the logo

Below the incorrect use of the 5GMETA logo is represented. This misuse consists in significant alterations of the logo's colour and size.

Figure 7: Incorrect use of 5GMETA logo

Fonts

5GMETA’s primary identity typeface is The Sans, to be used in all printed and web materials. It is recommended to use 12 of the 56 styles available, to be chosen according to the specific material and criteria of the designer.

As a basic rule, use The Sans Extrabold in the main heading. For subheadings, use The Sans Bold. For body copy, use The Sans Light.

The Sans

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890,./=+&_@!(%)\$|?>”:

Mintur min corem quia etur?

Tiurepudis et qui beatus, odita sam, imaxim valoris

Des que nimporio opta es que earcid utesequis ent, ut alitatem qui asit illesequisti alique lam estis maiorem. Itatem quuntem sam quae es simus atis reperatemp nonsequ iaspercim doluptatae cullaccat eatum eum et est, utPellessi dolent, simoluptur, qui nus volupta quas isi in et essunto minte autem et ut provitium facitae odi debis ad ut vollupt atestrum dolores solupienis et ute nonecep erist, consedi temquia videllescil magnimp errorer ovidebi tiurepudis et qui beatus, odita sam, imaxim valoris nimi, culpa quos exerum as aut estiasp no.

- Light
- Light Italic
- Plain
- Plain Italic
- SemiBold
- SemiBold Italic
- Bold
- Bold Italic
- Extrabold
- Extrabold Italic
- Black
- Black Italic

Figure 8: Font for printed and web material

The official font for office materials is Arial.

Arial

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890,./=+&_£@!(%)\$|?>”:

Arial Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890,./=+&_£@!(%)\$|?>”:

Figure 9: Font for printed office material

